

Evaluating the Interactions of CO₂-Ionic Liquid Systems through Molecular Modeling

S. Yamini Sudha, and Ashok Khanna

Abstract—Owing to the stringent environmental legislations, CO₂ capture and sequestration is one of the viable solutions to reduce the CO₂ emissions from various sources. In this context, Ionic liquids (ILs) are being investigated as suitable absorption media for CO₂ capture. Due to their non-evaporative, non-toxic, and non-corrosive nature, these ILs have the potential to replace the existing solvents like aqueous amine solutions for CO₂ separation technologies. Thus, the present work aims at studying the important aspects such as the interactions of CO₂ molecule with different anions (F⁻, Br⁻, Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, BF₄⁻, PF₆⁻, Tf₂N⁻, and CF₃SO₃⁻) that are commonly used in ILs through molecular modeling. In this, the minimum energy structures have been obtained using Ab initio based calculations at MP2 (Moller-Plesset perturbation) level. Results revealed various degrees of distortion of CO₂ molecule (from its linearity) with the anions studied, most likely due to the Lewis acid-base interactions between CO₂ and anion. Furthermore, binding energies for the anion-CO₂ complexes were also calculated. The implication of anion-CO₂ interactions to the solubility of CO₂ in ionic liquids is also discussed.

Keywords—CO₂, Ionic liquids, capture, molecular modeling, sequestration.

I. INTRODUCTION

ESCALATING concentrations of CO₂ and other greenhouse gases (GHG) in the Earth's atmosphere have the potential add to the natural greenhouse effect, which may result in climatic changes [1]. A major contributor to increased atmospheric CO₂ levels is fossil fuel combustion. Therefore, energy industry can be part of the solution to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by capturing and permanently sequestering CO₂ [2]. Carbon sequestration, which captures CO₂ from large point sources such as fossil fuel-fired electrical power-generation plants, and stores it in geological formations, has been proposed as a prominent solution to this problem. Efficient separation of CO₂ is a prominent solution to the economically viable sequestration efforts. The current methods of CO₂ capturing include, (a) absorbing into amine based solvents (b) carbonate based systems (c) ammonia based wet scrubbing (d) separation through polymeric membranes like Polyether-polyimide copolymer (e) adsorption on to carbonate based sorbents and amine based sorbents, and (f) metal organic frame works[3].

Ashok Khanna is with Department of Chemical Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India (corresponding author, phone: +91-512-2597117; e-mail: akhanna@iitk.ac.in).

S. Yamini Sudha is a PhD student in Department of Chemical Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India (e-mail: yaminis@iitk.ac.in).

However, these methods have certain disadvantages like energy intensive, amine loss and degradation, release of volatile organic compounds, and equipment corrosion [4].

Ionic liquids are a new and exciting class of compounds that have the potential to overcome many of the problems associated with the current CO₂ capture techniques. Ionic liquids (ILs) are organic salts that are liquid in their pure state near ambient conditions [5]. Typical ILs usually have either imidazolium, quaternary ammonium, pyrrolidinium, pyridinium, or tetra alkylphosphonium as the base for the cation. Possible anions include hexafluorophosphate [PF₆]⁻, tetrafluoroborate [BF₄]⁻, bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl) imide [(CF₃SO₂)₂N]⁻, triflate [CF₃SO₃]⁻, acetate [CH₃CO₂]⁻, trifluoroacetate [CF₃CO₂]⁻, nitrate [NO₃]⁻, chloride [Cl]⁻, bromide [Br]⁻ or iodide [I]⁻, among many others [6,7]. Adjusting the structure of either the anion or the cation can have huge effects on many properties including melting points, viscosities, densities, and gas and liquid solubilities [8]. ILs are regarded as potentially environmentally-benign solvents due to their immeasurably low vapor pressure, which essentially eliminates the opportunity for solvent release to the atmosphere [9]. ILs can dissolve CO₂ and are stable at temperatures up to several hundred degrees centigrade. Since ILs have excellent thermal stability, these can be used extensively for the recovery of CO₂ from flue gas. CO₂ interacts with the anion through a weak Lewis-acid-base interaction. Gases with large dipole moments (e.g. water) or quadrupole moments (e.g. CO₂ and N₂O), as well as the gases (eg: SO₂, NO_x) which have an opportunity for hydrogen bonding have the highest solubilities in the ILs [10]. Changing the cation from imidazolium to quaternary ammonium or pyrrolidinium, all with a similar anion, makes little difference in the CO₂ and O₂ solubilities. Anions containing fluorine such as bis[(trifluoromethyl) - sulfonyl] imide, Tf₂N⁻ have great affinity toward CO₂. Thus, anion in ILs plays an important role in the CO₂ absorption. Previous studies showed that CO₂ solubility for 1-butyl- 3-methylimidazolium ([bmim]⁺) based ILs at 60 °C increased in the order: nitrate ([NO₃]⁻) < tetrafluoroborate ([BF₄]⁻) < dicyanamide ([DCA]⁻) ~ hexafluorophosphate ([PF₆]⁻) ~ trifluoro methanesulfonate ([TfO]⁻) < bis[(trifluoro methyl)-sulfonyl] imide ([Tf₂N]⁻) < tris (trifluoro methylsulfonyl) methide ([methide]⁻) [11]. For the cation, the CO₂ solubility increases with increasing chain length of alkyl substituents. Due to the variety of possible cations and anions, there are virtually an infinite number of possible combinations, which means there should be ample opportunities to tailor and optimize the properties of these

solvents for CO₂ capture. For example, Bates et al[10]. developed a task²-specific ionic liquid for CO₂ capture by introducing an amine (-NH₂) group to the ionic liquid. These amine tethered ILs show substantial increase in CO₂ solubility than usual ionic liquids. Recently it was found that polymerization of Ionic Liquid monomers into Poly Ionic Liquids increases CO₂ absorption capacity 6 to 8 times [12]. These Poly ILs are made by Free radical polymerization or atom transfer radical polymerization. Since these poly ILs are solids, they can be made into finer particles and can be used as promising solid sorbents and as membrane materials for CO₂ capture and separation from flue gases[12].

II. INTERACTION OF CO₂ WITH IONIC LIQUID THROUGH AB INITIO (MP2-MOLLER PLESSET PERTURBATION LEVEL)

The solubility of CO₂ in ionic liquids has been the subject of experimental and theoretical investigations, but aspects concerning the molecular sites in the ionic liquids to which CO₂ associates more strongly can be studied through molecular simulations [13]. Ab initio calculations at the MP2 (Moller plesset) level of theory provide an insight into the nature of CO₂ interaction with ionic liquids [14]. Since the solubility of CO₂ in a particular IL mainly depends on the interaction of CO₂ with the type of anion of the IL, there is a need to study how CO₂ is interacting with different anions. In this paper we report Ab initio based zero Kelvin calculations that explore minimum energy structures of several anion-CO₂ pairs in gas phase helps in anticipating the interaction [15]. Anticipating the results, among all the anions studied, fluorine based anions show greater affinity towards CO₂. It was also observed that the solubility of CO₂ is inversely proportional to the anion-CO₂ binding energy. The distortion in the geometry of CO₂ is due to the interaction between the anion-CO₂.

Molecular Modeling Details

Geometry optimizations of different anions were carried out using ab-initio (MP2 (Moller-Plesset perturbation) level) calculations with 6-311+G* basis set using GAUSSIAN 03 software[17]. Anions like fluoride (F⁻), chloride (Cl⁻), bromide (Br⁻), nitrate (NO₃⁻), tetrafluoroborate(BF₄⁻), hexafluorophosphate (PF₆⁻), trifluoromethylsulfonyl (CF₃SO₃⁻), bis-(trifluoromethyl sulfonyl) imide (N[CF₃SO₃⁻]₂) were studied in the present study. The input for the simulation was the Z-matrix of the molecule that was made in MOLDEN (software used to visualize the molecules) [16]. Initially each anion is geometry optimized. Thermo chemistry of each of the anion obtained through frequency optimization. For each of the anion, CO₂ molecule was placed at different positions around the anion to explore the potential energy surface better. The structures and binding energies reported here are those corresponding to the lowest energies. The binding energy of each pair was obtained by subtracting the total energy of the isolated anion and that of isolated CO₂ molecule from the total energy of the pair. The minimum distance of CO₂ from the anion, the distortion in the structure, and the binding energy between CO₂ and anion were obtained and are presented in the Table I. A comparison between the present data and the

literature values (given in the brackets [15]) is also made in Table I.

The experimental solubility values of CO₂ in different [bmim] based ILs with various anions was used for establishing a relationship between binding energy and solubility [8].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Of all the anions studied, it is clear from Table I that the fluorine reacts spontaneously with CO₂ molecule to form FCO₂⁻, with a distance of 1.51 Å. Though the distance is larger when compared to the F-C bond distance in carbon tetra fluoride (1.355 Å), the formation of the bond was clear. The CO₂ molecule in the complex was highly distorted from its original linear structure showing a O-C-O bond angle of 137.92°. The binding energy of the complex was found to be -105.1 kJ/mol. The complex appears to be a distorted planar trigonal structure. The CO₂ molecule was found to bend away from the F⁻ ion in order to minimize the interaction between the electronegative fluorine and the oxygen. Furthermore, comparison of the data for halide ions showed a systematic trend with increasing halogen size: the distance of the carbon atom from the halide ion increases; the OCO angle increases; and the binding energy of the CO₂-halide complex decreases. The optimized structural configuration for Bromide – CO₂ dimer is shown in the Fig. 1.

TABLE I
COMPARISONS FOR NEAREST DISTANCE OF ANION IN THE CORRESPONDING COMPLEX, OCO BOND ANGLE AND BINDING ENERGY

Anion	Min Distance (Å)	OCO Angle (°)	Binding energy (kJ/mol)	Solubility in bmim IL
F ⁻	1.51 (1.59)	137.92 (139.4)	-105.1, (-118.3)	-
Cl ⁻	2.89 (2.75)	171.59 (162.2)	-22.86 (-26.9)	0.26
Br ⁻	3.14 (3.09)	173.46 (167.6)	-19.38 (-20.7)	0.31
NO ₃ ⁻	2.74 (2.75)	172.47 (172.6)	-25.46 (-24.8)	0.22
BF ₄ ⁻	2.76 (2.77)	175.1 (175.1)	-19.5 (-18.8)	0.30
PF ₆ ⁻	2.78 (2.80)	176.1 (176.1)	-14.0 (13.8)	0.31
Tf ₂ N ⁻	3.00 (2.84)	179.8 (176.9)	-7.8 (-9.9)	0.42
CF ₃ SO ₃ ⁻	3.39 (2.91)	173.4 (175.4)	-10.705 (-14.6)	0.34

The geometry of the dimer was similar for the other halogen anions except for the C-X distance and the OCO angle. All the mono atomic anions were observed to lie in the plane of the CO₂ molecule. Furthermore, CO₂ has bent away

from the anions so as to minimize the repulsive interaction of the oxygen atoms with the halide ions. Other anions that exhibited a greater affinity towards CO₂ molecules were NO₃⁻, BF₄⁻, PF₆⁻, Tf₂N⁻, and CF₃SO₃⁻.

Fig. 1 Minimum energy structure of Bromide-CO₂ dimer

Fig. 2 shows the minimum energy geometries of some of the anions studied with CO₂. It was observed that in the complex with NO₃⁻, CO₂ is located in such a way that it is equidistance from the two oxygens of nitrate ion with the carbon of CO₂ lying in the plane of the anion. Also the oxygens of the CO₂ bent outwards to reduce the repulsive interaction with the electronegative oxygens of the nitrate ion. In the tetrafluoroborate-CO₂ complex, the carbon of CO₂ lies in the plane formed by two BF bond vectors and the CO₂ molecule is perpendicular to this plane just as in the case of nitrate ion.

Fig. 2 Minimum energy structures of different anion-CO₂ complexes (a) NO₃⁻ (b) BF₄⁻ (c) PF₆⁻ (d) CF₃SO₃⁻

It was reported that the optimized structures of anion-CO₂ complexes mainly dominated by Lewis acid-base interactions, with the carbon atom of CO₂ as the electron acceptor (acid) and the anion as the donor (base). This interaction leads to the varying degrees of distortion of the CO₂ molecule. The extent of bending of CO₂ is generally considered to be a measure of the basicity of the anion.

Fig. 3 Binding energy of anion-CO₂ dimer versus deviation of OCO angle of CO₂ molecule from 180° in various complexes. The dots represent various anions. The continuous line is the best fit to the data

Furthermore, the variation of binding energy with OCO angle deviation (from linearity) is illustrated in Fig. 3 for different anions studied. It appears that the extent of distortion from the linear geometry upon complexation appears to be proportional to the binding energy.

It is also clear from Table I that the anions containing fluoro-alkyl groups (Tf₂N⁻, CF₃SO₃⁻) possess lower binding energies of anion-CO₂ complex compared to that of inorganic fluorine-based anion (F⁻, BF₄⁻, PF₆⁻) complexes. This in turn results in the higher CO₂ solubilities (see Fig. 4) for fluoro-alkyl groups.

Fig. 4 Comparison of experimentally measured solubility of CO₂ in ionic liquids of different anions containing the same cation (bmim) with binding energy of corresponding complex

IV. CONCLUSION

The interactions of CO₂ molecule with various anions (F⁻, Br⁻, Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, BF₄⁻, PF₆⁻, Tf₂N⁻, and CF₃SO₃⁻) employed in

ionic liquids have been studied using Ab initio (MP2 level) calculations. The anion-CO₂ interactions revealed various degrees of distortions (OCO angle) of CO₂ molecule from its linearity, presumably due to the role of Lewis acid-base interaction between CO₂ and the anions. In case of halide ions, the interaction strength (binding energy) found to be decreased with increasing size of anion. Furthermore, the binding energy of CO₂-anion complexes was observed to be inversely proportional to the solubility of CO₂ in the respective ionic liquid.

[17] Frisch MJ, Trucks GW, Schlegel HB, Scuseria GE, Robb MA, heeseman JR, Montgomery JA, Vreven T, Kudin KN, Burant JC, Millam JM, Iyengar SS, Tomasi J, Barone V, Mennucci B, Cossi M, Scalmani G, Rega N, Petersson GA, Nakatsuji H, Hada M, Ehara M, Toyota K, Fukuda R, Hasegawa J, Ishida M, Nakajima T, Honda Y, Kitao O, Nakai H, Klene M, Li X, Knox JE, Hratchian HP, Cross JB, Adamo C, Jaramillo J, Gomperts R, Stratmann RE, Yazyev O, Austin AJ, Cammi R, Pomelli C, Ochterski JW, Ayala PY, Morokuma K, Voth GA, Salvador P, Dannenberg JJ, Zakrzewski VG, Dapprich S, Daniels AD, Strain MC, Farkas O, Malick DK, Rabuck AD, Raghavachari K, Foresman JB, Ortiz JV, Cui Q, Baboul AG, Clifford S, Cioslowski J, Stefanov BB, Liu G, Liashenko A, Piskorz P, Komaromi I, Martin RL, Fox DJ, Keith T, Al-Laham MA, Peng CY, Nanayakkara A, Challacombe M, Gill PMW, Johnson B, Chen W, Wong MW, Gonzalez C, Pople JA (2004) Gaussian 03, Revision C.02. Gaussian Inc, Wallingford

REFERENCES

- [1] T. L. Jhon, S. M. Klara, G. M. Howard and R. D. Srivastava, "An overview of terrestrial sequestration of carbon dioxide: The United states Department of Energy's Fossil energy R&D program," Climatic Change, 2006, 74, pp. 81-95.
- [2] M. K. Scott, R. D. Srivastava and G. M. Howard, "Integrated collaborative technology development program for CO₂ sequestration in geologic formations—United States Department of Energy R&D", Energy Conversion and Management, 2003, 44, pp. 2699-2712.
- [3] J. D. Figueroa, T. Fout, S. Plasynski, H. McIlvried and R. D. Srivastava "Advances in CO₂ capture technology-The US.Department of Energy's Carbon Sequestration Program", International journal of Greenhouse Gas Control, 2008, 2, pp. 9-20.
- [4] C. Cadena, J. L. Anthony, J. K. Shaw, T. I. Morrow, J. F. Brennecke and E. J. Maginn, "Why CO₂ so soluble in imidazolium based Ionic Liquids?", Journal of American Chemical Society, 2004, 126, pp. 5300-5308.
- [5] L. A. Blanchard, Gu Z, J. F. Brennecke, "High pressure phase behavior of IL/CO₂ systems", Journal of Physical Chemistry B, 2001, 105, pp. 2437-2444.
- [6] J. L. Anthony, and E. J. Maginn, "Ostwald thermodynamics of imidazolium based ionic liquids and water", Journal of Physical Chemistry B, 2001, 105, pp. 10942-10949.
- [7] J. L. Anthony and E. J. Maginn, "Solubilities and thermodynamic properties of gases in the ionic liquid 1-n-butyl-3-methylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate", Journal of Physical Chemistry B, 2002, 106, pp. 7315-7320.
- [8] N. V. K. Sudhir, R. M. Berlyn, M. S. Eric and J. F. Brennecke, "High pressure phase behavior of carbon dioxide with imidazolium based Ionic Liquids", Journal of Physical Chemistry B, 2004, 108, pp. 20355-20365.
- [9] P. Scovazzo, J. Kieft, D. A. Finan, C. Koval, D. Dubois and R. Noble, « Gas separations using non-hexafluorophosphate [PF₆]- anion supported ionic liquid membranes », Journal of Membrane Science, 2004, 238, pp. 57-63.
- [10] E. D. Bates, R. D. Mayton, N. Ioanna and J. H. Davis, "CO₂ capture by a Task-Specific Ionic Liquid", Journal of American chemical society, 2002, 124, pp. 6.
- [11] M. J. Muldoon, N. V. K. Sudhir, J. L. Anderson, J. K. Dixon and J. F. Brennecke, "Improving carbon dioxide solubility in Ionic Liquids", Journal of Physical Chemistry B, 2007, 111, pp. 9001-9009.
- [12] T. Jianbin, W. Sun, H. Tang, M. Radosz and Y. Shen, "Enhanced CO₂ Absorption of Poly(ionic liquid)s," Macromolecules, 2005, 38, pp. 2037-2039.
- [13] N. Karl, J. Kirschner, P. Bowen and J. B. Sorensen, "Calculating Interaction Energies Using First Principle Theories: Consideration of Basis Set Superposition Error and Fragment Relaxation", Journal of Chemical Education, 2007, 84, pp. 7.
- [14] J.K.Shah and E.J. Maginn, "Monte Carlo Simulations of Gas Solubility in the Ionic Liquid 1-n- Butyl -3 -methyl imidazolium Hexafluorophosphate", Journal of Physical Chemistry B, 2005, 109, pp.10395-10405.
- [15] B. L. Bhargava and S. Balasubramanian, "Probing anion-carbon dioxide interactions in room temperature ionic liquids: Gas phase cluster calculations", Chemical Physics Letters, 2007, 444, pp. 242-246.
- [16] G.Schaftenaar and J.H.Noordik, "Molden: a pre-and post-processing program for molecular and electronic structures", Journal of Computer Aided Molecular Design, 2000, 14, pp.123-134.